

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

PHYSICAL THERAPY: FROM NON-SURGICAL CONSERVATIVE MANAGEMENT TO POST-SURGICAL MANAGEMENT LEVEL OF SATISFACTION BY ORTHOPAEDIC SURGEONS.

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Article Received: August 2019

Accepted: September 2019

Published: October 2019

Abstract:

Orthopedic surgery is very vast field and with the advancement in technology it has been very difficult for orthopedic surgeons to do everything by themselves due to time and work overload. This role of physiotherapist is yet to be accepted in the Pakistan as well as other underdeveloped countries but the process of admiring the justified role has begun. Orthopedic Surgeons have shown the level of trust on the physiotherapist in the management of certain illnesses in the current research by us in the historical city of Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan with well-known Universities with reliable orthopedic units supported by private sector hospitals. We selected 100 Doctors of both genders involved in orthopedic care from Consultant orthopedic surgeon to PG Trainees from Liaquat University Hospital, Isra University Hospital and Bone Care Hospital through convenient sampling. The response was obtained on a self-designed questionnaire to assess the level of satisfaction among the orthopedic doctors. Data was analyzed through Chi-square on SPSS version 22 and 0.05 significance level. We found 100% in favor of physiotherapy to be used in variety of pre and post-surgical conditions. There was significant level of orthopedic surgeon and patient satisfaction p-0.0035.

Conclusion: *Orthopedic Surgeons have shown significant levels of satisfaction on physiotherapist in the conservative management and postsurgical management of certain orthopedic conditions.*

Keywords: *Physical Therapy, Conservative, Post-Surgical, Advanced Practice Physiotherapist, Orthopedic Surgeons.*

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Please cite this article in press Marish Memon et al., *Physical Therapy: From Non-Surgical Conservative Management to Post-Surgical Management Level of Satisfaction by Orthopaedic Surgeons.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(10).

INTRODUCTION:

With advancement in of technology human life is prone to more risks such as increased number of accident and trauma cases. The rise in number of the trauma cases as well as improved modifications in the health care systems the importance of physical therapy is also increasing day by day. Orthopedic surgeons are too busy not only in dealing with the trauma but also other variety of conditions like joint replacement, deformity corrections, limb lengthening, tendon repair and transfer. These surgeons are countering other general orthopedic problems such as osteoarthritis, frozen shoulder, neck pain, backache, gouty arthritis, tumor surgery and many other musculoskeletal problems. Most of these require prolonged period of physiotherapy for which the orthopedic surgeon refers these cases to physiotherapist that greatly helps in improving early rehabilitation and better surgical outcomes. So the need of physical therapist raised and some developed countries adopted the system of APP (Advanced Practice Physiotherapist) to save the time of the surgeon and patient for non-surgical orthopedic and musculoskeletal problems [1,2,5]. Un-justified referrals are reported by general physicians from pediatric and adult patients worthy of being managed by physiotherapy. Physical therapy can effectively manage the conservative nature of orthopedic cases as well as many postsurgical orthopedic patients for avoiding strictures, disability as a tool of rehabilitation [1,2]. It is reported by certain studies that 55% - 90% cases referred to orthopaedic surgeons are not justified candidates for surgical procedures and such cases would likely have benefited from conservative management [3,4].

METHODOLOGY:

This work of research was carried out at Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan in three different hospitals, Liaquat University Hospital, bone care hospital and Isra University Hospital. Our study population was 100 doctors providing the orthopedic serves and the required information was acquired through self-designed proforma. Non-probability sampling was used as convenient to select consultant orthopedic surgeons (Professors, Associate Professors, Assistant Professors), Registrars, PG trainees and medical officers. Study inclusions were male and female doctors concerned orthopedic care including the trainees while study exclusions were non- willing orthopedic doctors, specialties other than orthopedic, house surgeons and paramedical staff. Frequency and percentage were calculated Chi-square was used for level of satisfaction of patients and doctors at 0.05 level of significance SPSS version 21.

RESULTS:

Participating doctors were 61(61%) from Liaquat University Hospital, while 30(30%) and 9(9%) were from Bone Care and Isra University Hospitals respectively. Male doctors were 60 (60%) whereas female doctors were 40 (40%) fig 1. Doctors showing satisfaction with the practice of physiotherapists were 83(83%) while 17(17%) doctors were not satisfied however 95(95%) doctors reported patient satisfaction with physiotherapist and only 05(5%) doctors reported un-satisfaction of patients about physiotherapy p-value 0.0035(Table 1). Levels of satisfaction about the role of physiotherapists in various orthopedic conditions are shown in table 2.

Table1. Chi-square of Orthopedic Surgeon and Patient Satisfaction

S. No.	Parameters	Yes	No	Chi-Square	P-Value
1.	Orthopedic Surgeon Satisfaction	83(83%)	17(17%)	7.35	0.0035
2.	Patient Satisfaction	95(95%)	05(5%)		

Table2.Level of orthopedic Surgeon satisfaction in various conditions

S. No.	Parameters	Yes	No
1.	Role in Post-operative pain management	100 (100%)	00 (0%)
2.	Role in Musculoskeletal conditions?	100 (100%)	00 (0%)
3.	Role in other Orthopedic Conditions	100 (100%)	00 (0%)
4.	Role in Neck pain	100 (100%)	00 (0%)
5.	Role in Stroke Rehabilitation	100 (100%)	00 (0%)
6.	Role in Parkinsonism related muscular problems	100 (100%)	00 (0%)
7.	Role in developmental delay in children	99 (99%)	01 (1%)

Figure1. Showing gender distribution of Doctors

DISCUSSION:

Physical therapy is the demand of the time with life style and cultural modification human beings are facing a lot of musculoskeletal disorders. The number of one year knee joint replacements surgeries in UK was reported to be 75,000 while these were 719000 in USA requiring physiotherapy as rehabilitation [6]. Studies suggest non-significant differences between the diagnostic approach of orthopedic surgeons and advance practice physiotherapists with the exception of extra investigations and excessive use of NSAIDs for Osteoarthritis that is quite justified as per recommended guideline for NSAIDs use [7]. Physical therapy is much beneficial for normal healthy individual to maintain the good health and it works as a preventive measure against the future diseases like wise it is of prime importance in many non-surgical musculoskeletal disorders and many other diseases of various body systems. Both the doctors and the physiotherapists have this responsibility to counsel patients to adopt the physical activity on regular basis [8, 9]. Kennedy DM et al (2010) reported high level of satisfaction from the patients on the APP (advance practice physiotherapist p-value 0.014[10]. He analyzed 83 patients on physiotherapist-led triage and 80 patients on standard practice. Participants of study perceived significant difference between the two with higher quality of care went into the favor of triage as

compared to standard practice p-value 0.001 on the basis of examination as well as treatment. C. Jenkins et al (2019) reported knee joint replacement therapy more satisfactory when performed along with physiotherapist [12]. That much work is not seen in Pakistan because the public is doctor centered very difficult to change the public mind, hopefully things will change overtime. Current work has certain limitations but hopefully it will support to serve the patient cause. The level of Doctor and patient satisfaction remained significant statistically p-value 0.0035 that was consistent to all mentioned studies. We strongly recommend APP mediated triage system for all orthopedic units in Pakistan as well as other countries around the globe for better patient care.

CONCLUSION:

Orthopedic doctors were found to be well satisfied with physiotherapists

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